

POTENTIAL LOCAL ANAESTHETICS. PART I. SYNTHESIS OF
BASIC *N*-BENZYLACETAMIDES

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N-(subst. benzyl)-chloroacetamides have been condensed with secondary amines to yield dialkylamino-, morpholinyl- and piperidiny-*N*-(subst. benzyl)-acetamides.

Basic anilides in a large number have been synthesised, and amongst these diethylamino-2:6-dimethylacetanilide, Xylocaine, is the best known local anaesthetic (Lofgren and Lundquist, U.S.P. 2, 441,498/1948; *Chem. Abst.*, 1948, 42, 6378).

Benzyl alcohol possesses local anaesthetic properties (Maecht, *J. Pharmacol. Expt. Therap.*, 1918, 11, 263) and *N*-benzyl- β -chloropropionamide shows anticonvulsant properties (Kushner *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1951, 16, 1283). It was therefore thought of interest to prepare basic amides containing benzyl group. With this object in view dialkylamino-, morpholinyl- and piperidiny-*N*-benzylacetamides have been prepared and described in this communication. Chloroacetyl chloride was allowed to react with benzylamines and the chloroacetyl-*N*-benzylamides were heated with secondary amines to yield the required basic amides. Hydrochlorides of compounds: (1) diethylamino-*N*-(*m*-methylbenzyl)-, (2) diethylamino-*N*-(*p*-methylbenzyl)- and (3) diethylamino-*N*-(*o*-chlorobenzyl)-acetamides (compounds No. 2, 3 and 4 respectively of Table II) were examined for local anaesthetic properties by the intra-dermal anaesthesia method of Bülbring and Wajda (*J. Pharmacol.*, 1945, 85, 78) and were found to be active at 0.05% concentration.

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzylamines were prepared from the corresponding benzyl halides by the method of Graymore (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 293; 1947, 1116).

Condensation of Benzylamines with Chloroacetyl Chloride.—To the amine (1 g.), suspended in water (5 c.c.) and cooled in an ice-salt mixture, were added dropwise with vigorous shaking chloroacetyl chloride and NaOH (10%, 5 c.c.) simultaneously. After allowing the reaction mixture to attain room temperature, the precipitate was filtered and washed with cold water, HCl (1:1), and finally with water. The substances crystallised in needles from dilute ethanol (Table I).

TABLE I

N-Benzyl-chloroacetamides.

S. No.	R.	M.P.	Formula.	% Chlorine.	
				Found.	Calc.
1	<i>o</i> -Me	95°	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ ONCl	17.8	18.0
2	<i>m</i> -Me	48°	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ ONCl	17.9	18.0
3	<i>p</i> -Me	85°	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ ONCl	17.8	18.0
4	<i>o</i> -Cl	125°	C ₉ H ₉ ONCl ₂	32.4	32.6
5	<i>m</i> -Cl	64-65°	C ₉ H ₉ ONCl ₂	32.8	32.6
6	<i>p</i> -Cl	75°	C ₉ H ₉ ONCl ₂	32.7	32.6
7	3:4-Dimethyl	88°	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ ONCl	16.8	16.8
8	2:4-Dimethyl	96°	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ ONCl	16.9	16.8
9	2:5-Dimethyl	106°	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ ONCl	16.7	16.8

Condensation of Secondary Amines with N-Benzyl-chloroacetamide.—A mixture of *N*-benzyl-chloroacetamide (0.015 *M*) and secondary amine (0.03 *M*) in absolute ethanol (20 c.c.) was refluxed for 4 hours. Alcohol was distilled off and the residue was treated with a saturated NaHCO_3 solution, and the thick oily mass was dissolved in dilute HCl , filtered and treated with NH_4OH solution to liberate the base. The oily base was extracted with ether, dried and converted into the hydrochloride (by passing dry HCl gas into dry ethereal solution). The hydrochlorides crystallised in needles from acetone. The compounds prepared are shown in Tables II, III and IV.

TABLE II

Hydrochlorides of diethylamino-N-(subst.-benzyl)-acetamides.

S. No.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.
1	200°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{ON}_2\text{HCl}$	10.2	10.4
2	220°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{ON}_2\text{HCl}$	10.3	10.4
3	185°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{ON}_2\text{HCl}$	10.6	10.4
4	170°	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{19}\text{ON}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{HCl}$	9.4	9.6
5	195°	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{19}\text{ON}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{HCl}$	9.5	9.6
6	210°	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{19}\text{ON}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{HCl}$	9.5	9.6
7	205°	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{25}\text{ON}_2\text{HCl}$	9.7	9.8
8	195°	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{25}\text{ON}_2\text{HCl}$	9.6	9.8
9	130°	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{25}\text{ON}_2\text{HCl}$	9.9	9.8

* R serially same as in Table I.

TABLE III

Hydrochlorides of morpholinyl-N-(subst.-benzyl)-acetamides.

S. No.	R.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.
1	<i>o</i> -Me	210°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{HCl}$	10.0	9.8
2	<i>m</i> -Me	160°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{HCl}$	9.9	8
3	<i>p</i> -Me	280°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{HCl}$	9.7	9.8
4	<i>o</i> -Cl	180°	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{HCl}$	9.2	9.2
5	<i>p</i> -Cl	240°	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{HCl}$	9.0	9.2

TABLE IV

Hydrochlorides of piperidinyll-N-(subst.-benzyl)-acetamides.

S. No.	R.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.
1	<i>p</i> -Me	202°	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ ON ₂ .HCl	10.0	9.9
2	<i>o</i> -Cl	110°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ON ₂ Cl ₂ .HCl	9.2	9.2

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